

Tracing the Network Continuity: From the Socialist to the Communist Women's Movement (1907–1934)

Minja Bujakovic [1]

1: European University Institute (EUI)

Bujakovic Minja. 2024. "Tracing the Network Continuity: From the Socialist to the Communist Women's Movement (1907-1934)", *Historical Network Research* 2024, Lausanne, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12664672

In my work, I explore the intertwined history of the Socialist Women's Movement (SWM) (1907-1917) and the Communist Women's Movement (CWM) (1920-1934). By examining these two movements, I aim to investigate the role of network continuity as a facet of the continuity of left-wing women's activism. To do so, I focus on the SWM network as a pre-existing CWM network. The idea of a movement emerging from a pre-existing network is not new – it is solidified in the theory of collective organising and discussed in the literature as one of the most successful strategies for establishing a new movement and/or organisation. As Nick Crossley noted, the pre-existing ties imply the existence of coordination, channels of communication, esprit de corps, and a division of labour with the lines of authority; these factors, thus, serve as predictors of collective action, significantly accelerating the movement's development.²⁷ Even though this argument has also been highlighted in the research on the history of women's movements and activism, in the case of the SWM and CWM, its implications and significance have not been thoroughly examined.²⁸

Recognising the intrinsic link and continuity between the SWM and its successor is not a mere observation but an insight made by the movement participants. Clara Zetkin, serving as a secretary for both movements, provided a basis for the argument of continuity, stating: “At a higher level of historical, theoretical knowledge and practical activity, the Communist Women's Movement [...] is today using what the Social-Democratic women's movement started but betrayed.”²⁹ This statement, along with other discussions of communist activists, underscores the importance of examining the SWM network to comprehend the CWM's development fully. Therefore, I start my research by examining the network of the SWM through the lens of Historical Network Research (HNR), seeing it as a transnational network of collaboration and communication among left-wing women activists and an organisational base for the future CWM. To reconstruct it, I focus on four international SWM conferences held between 1907 and 1917: Stuttgart (1907), Copenhagen (1910), Bern (1915), and Stockholm (1917). These conferences constituted spaces where internationalism was practised, although, in the case of the SWM, internationalism predominantly remained within the confines of Western Europe. Moreover, women activists recognised that international women's conferences played an essential role in mobilising and recruiting for their movement by establishing new ties among activists while reinforcing, evolving, or occasionally dissolving existing ones. Still, The network forged through the conferences was essential for spreading and exchanging ideas, information, and strategies, significantly contributing to the movement's growth.

²⁷ Nick Crossley, “Social Networks and Extraparliamentary Politics,” *Sociology Compass* 1, no. 1 (September 2007): 230. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9020.2007.00003.x>.

²⁸ Aldon D. Morris and Carol McClurg Mueller, eds., *Frontiers in Social Movement Theory* (New Haven, Conn: Yale University Press, 1992), 162. On the scholarship on women's movements and international networks of collaboration see also: Bonnie Anderson: *Joyous Greetings: The First International Women's Movement, 1830–1860.*; Krista Cowman, “The Women's Movement and Internationalism in the 20th Century,” *Moving the Social*, October 14, 2016, 55-74. <https://doi.org/10.13154/MTS.55.2016.55-74>. Patricia Ward D'Itri: *Cross Currents in the International Women's Movements, 1848– 1948*, Bowling Green Ohio 1998; In the case of the SWM and CWM, author Mike Taber acknowledged the CWM's ambition to draw from the SWM legacies while rectifying its shortcomings.

²⁹ Communist Women, Bourgeois Women, Social- Democratic Women, 1931, Fond 528, Description 1, Reel 6, File 1863, International Institute for Social History, Amsterdam, Netherlands, 42.

Seventy-five women activists who participated in these conferences constitute nodes in the network, connected with multiple kinds of ties, resulting in 1215 ties differing in thickness by weight. (Figure 1)

The difference between the ties is visually marked through the tie colour and the weight of the ties, represented by the thickness of the ties, ranging from 1 (events), 2 (same party membership), and 3 (personal relations). (Figure 2) The first kind of tie – event participation – is used to develop the movement network's general structure based on chosen representatives' participation in international conferences. Considering that these events gathered rather a small number of participants that would not pass 50, it is possible to assume that the actors present met each other or participated in the form of an exchange of ideas, either directly or through mediators. Further analysis of primary sources allowed for discovering different types of ties that connected the activists beyond these conferences, such as personal relations. Even though defining a tie as a personal relation could be disputable, primarily due to the impermanent character of the relations, in the case of the movement, the tie was defined as such when primary sources proved the existence of correspondence, meetings outside of the conferences, collaboration through other activities. The last kind of tie includes same-party membership, connecting activists through their activities in national parties, and creating cliques in the network. The cliques constitute an important part of this network, serving as hubs of communication and collaboration of activists from the same national parties, significantly affecting their participation in the movement.

The identification of the nodes represents the main challenge in the research. Given the SWM's semi-clandestine nature after the First World War outbreak, documents detailing its history do not consistently feature lists of conference participants. Consequently, the data is gathered from various sources, including conference reports, newspaper articles, letters, memoirs, and diaries. This suggests that the network of the movement likely encompassed more nodes than has been identified so far. Moreover, the strategic lack of documents that could connect activists with the network affected the character of the network, making it semi-covert. Due to this change, it is unclear whether new actors joined, especially the 1917 conference, which had a stronger left-wing orientation, and whether any of them subsequently joined the CWM. The political developments of 1917, especially the October Revolution, directly affected the movement, putting it in a state of abeyance. Abeyance, as explained by author Verta Taylor, “depicts a holding process by which movements sustain themselves in non-receptive political environments and provide continuity from one stage of mobilisation to another.”³⁰ The movement in abeyance, Taylor writes further, becomes a cadre of activists who create a niche for themselves.³¹ The political developments of 1917, including the October Revolution, led to the dissipation of the movement in correlation with other factors. With the success of the revolution and the establishment of the international organisation – Communist International, a portion of the SWM's activists found their “niche” within the CWM, established in 1920. Out of 75 activists, 22 joined the new movement. (Figure 3)

³⁰ Verta Taylor, “Social Movement Continuity: The Women's Movement in Abeyance,” *American Sociological Review* 54, no. 5 (1989): 761–75, <https://doi.org/10.2307/2117752>.

³¹ Ibid. 762.

Meanwhile, seven have passed away, one withdrew from politics, and the remaining 45 maintained their active roles primarily within socialist and social democratic parties, often engaging in formal political institutions and/or other women's organisations. Most women who opted not to align with the CWM belonged to tightly knitted cliques, maintaining strong connections with one another compared to the border network. (Figure 4)

The varied colours of the nodes signify diverse party affiliations, indicating that cliques primarily formed around the connections established within each national party. Focusing on these cliques, it is possible to hypothesise why activists decided not to join the CWM in relation to three factors: 1) tactical and ideological differences, 2) multiplexity and salience of ties, and 3) political restrictions and opportunities. Ideologically and strategically, while communist women viewed revolution and the establishment of a new social, economic, and political order as a route to women's emancipation, those aligned with socialist and social-democratic parties saw the solution in social reforms performed within the frameworks of the existing orders. Moreover, the connectedness within the cliques serves as a reminder that all the activists were embedded in multiple networks. Their decision not to join the CWM could be understood through the multiplexity and salience of ties, as joining a revolutionary organisation constituted a form of high-cost activism that would necessarily cut some of these ties and be aware of this cost. This dilemma was already discussed in 1915, with the SWM's involvement with the anti-war efforts, which some women rejected, fearing the accusation of treason by both the belligerent countries and their parties that supported the war. This was particularly the case after 1917: due to their semi-illegal character and the rise of the counterrevolutionary movements, joining communist parties constituted a high-cost activist choice restricting the political opportunities other parties offered. With the interplay of political opportunities and restrictions, the salience of ties, and often ideological affinities, many socialist women decided to stay in their previous organisations. Consequently, even 23 SWM members later assumed significant political roles, underscoring the nuanced decisions around movement participation.

The CWM's pre-existing network included 22 activists connected with 175 ties, making the network highly connected and tightly knitted. (Figure 5)

The pre-existing network predominantly comprised individuals linked by strong ties based on personal relations. This finding supports the theory that activists deciding to participate in high-risk activism were connected by strong personal ties and shared activist experience.³² Moreover, it confirms that prior ties,

³² Donatella Della Porta, *Clandestine Political Violence*, Cambridge Studies in Contentious Politics (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013), 159, 160.

next to a strong identification with the newly emerging movement, are crucial factors in encouraging high-cost activism, such as communist women's activism.³³ Therefore, strong ties garnered through the activism within the SWM, shared views on women's emancipation, and ideological proximity constituted structural factors that allowed the successful activation of the pre-existing network. This conclusion also underlines that the embeddedness in the network determines the effect of the pre-existing ties and enhances the potential for successful activism mobilisation through the existing network.

Furthermore, key figures within the CWM maintained and built upon their central roles from the previous movement, underscoring the legacy of effective leadership, mutual trust and commitment to a common cause. In the following years, communist women leveraged the ties established through the SWM: members of the pre-existing network participated as delegates at the CWM conferences, contributed to CWM publications, and developed ideas and strategies for the CWM. This underscores the indisputable role of the pre-existing network, which facilitated strong connections among activists and acted as a reservoir of tested ideas and collective experience. The evolution of the network from SWM to CWM showcases the significance of the preexisting network in maintaining the momentum of left-wing women's activism, suggesting the importance of further investigation into how these networks contributed to the movement's continuity, especially in the case of left-wing women's activism.

References

- Anderson, Bonnie S. *Joyous Greetings: The First International Women's Movement, 1830-1860*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2000.
- Cowman, Krista. "The Women's Movement and Internationalism in the 20th Century." *Moving the Social* 55 (October 14, 2016): 55-74. <https://doi.org/10.13154/MTS.55.2016.55-74>.
- Crossley, Nick. "Social Networks and Extraparliamentary Politics." *Sociology Compass* 1, no. 1 (September 2007): 222–36. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9020.2007.00003.x>.
- D'Itri, Patricia Ward. *Cross Currents in the International Women's Movements, 1848–1948*. Bowling Green, Ohio, 1998.
- Della Porta, Donatella. *Clandestine Political Violence*. Cambridge Studies in Contentious Politics. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013. <https://hdl.handle.net/1814/27278>.
- McAdam, Doug, and Ronnelle Paulsen. "Specifying the Relationship Between Social Ties and Activism." *American Journal of Sociology* 99, no. 3 (1993): 640-647.
- Morris, Aldon D., and Carol McClurg Mueller, eds. *Frontiers in Social Movement Theory*. New Haven, Conn: Yale University Press, 1992.
- Taber, Michael, and Daria Dyakonova, eds. *The Communist Women's Movement, 1920-1922: Proceedings, Resolutions, and Reports*. Historical Materialism Book Series, Vol. 268. Leiden; Boston: Brill, 2023.
- Taylor, Verta. "Social Movement Continuity: The Women's Movement in Abeyance." *American Sociological Review* 54, no. 5 (1989): 761–75. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2117752>.

³³ Doug McAdam and Ronnelle Paulsen, "Specifying the Relationship Between Social Ties and Activism," *American Journal of Sociology* 99, no. 3 (1993): 663.